

My submission to arXiv was rejected repeatedly

April 7, 2026

To whom it may concern,

I submitted several papers to arXiv, however, being rejected. Here are the title and numbers of these papers:

(1) Detailed Response regarding Series of Paper [Robust Estimation from Distribution Structures: III. Invariant Moments]; MOD-77994 arXiv submit/7126034;

(2) ALR-CA: Reclaiming Price-Setting Agency in the Age of Digital Gosplan; MOD-77994 arXiv submit/7126034; MOD-80574 arXiv submit/7155018;

(3) Stochastic Iterative UBI: Dynamics Equilibrium via Stochastic Distribution and Endogenous Tax-Feedback Loops; MOD-80078 arXiv submit/7177921;

(4) Option-embedded Perpetual Environment Debt; MOD-80442 arXiv submit/7204184;

(5) Anchoring Productivity: Stochastic Interference Games in Universal Basic Income; MOD-80329 arXiv submit/7180313;

(6) Reflections: The Collapse of Multilayer Predation and the Emergence of a Monolithic Leviathan; MOD-86816 arXiv submit/7353070.

These papers were already submitted to other preprint platforms and publicly accessible.

Sincerely,

Li Tuobang